

ECONOMICS OF INFORMATION SECURITY: PROBLEM FIELD AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Knyazkova Veronika Svyatoslavovna

associate professor, Department of Management, Belarusian State University of Informatics and
Radioelectronics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20337722>

Abstract: *This paper examines the main research areas in the conceptual field of economics of information security, provides a definition of the scientific field of "economics of information security", examines the specifics of standardization and information security management, and analyzes the tools and methodological apparatus of economics of information security (training, forecasting, assessment).*

Keywords: *information security, economics of information security, methodology, standardization, training, management, BSUIR.*

Modern theory of economics of information security seamlessly incorporates knowledge accumulated in various fields of scientific knowledge – economics, mathematics, philosophy, sociology, communication theory, information theory, cybersecurity, and jurisprudence. It also draws on the techniques and methods of these disciplines. At the same time, the economics of information security is an independent scientific field, with its own research subject within the pantheon of economic disciplines.

The economics of information security examines key concepts – information and security – from an economic perspective. It also utilizes a broad range of economic and mathematical tools, including methods of mathematical statistics, probability theory, and others.

In our opinion, the following issues in the economics of information security are currently the most pressing:

- conducting fundamental research on information issues in general, including developing a conceptual and categorical framework, refining and specifying research methods and tools;
- developing action plans for implementing national policies to improve information security at all levels of government;
- defining a mechanism for interconnecting information security activities across sectors of the national economy;
- improving legislation in the field of information security;
- harmonizing national standards with international ones, implementing best practices in information security into everyday activities;
- further improving the methodology for assessing and self-assessing organizational performance, and widely implementing modern methods of comprehensive information security management;
- developing theoretical foundations for identifying information security risks and threats and identifying optimal solutions for ensuring the information security of economic agents;

- developing a system of continuous education in the field of information security, and providing scientific and methodological support for training specialists at all levels.

In this article, we will define the economics of information security as a branch of economics that studies the financial and economic aspects of ensuring the security of information systems and data. The primary goal of economics of information security as a science is to study and analyze how organizations and governments should effectively allocate resources for information protection to minimize risks and losses from compromising the integrity, availability, and/or confidentiality of information [1].

This paper focuses on economic aspects of such activities in the field of information security as standardization and information security management.

In the field of information security, there are numerous standards that help organizations protect their data. It should be noted that a detailed analysis of standards, even the most frequently used ones, is a separate scientific question and even discipline. Therefore, here we will limit ourselves to mentioning the leading global organizations that develop standards that subsequently become the industry's gold standard. These include, of course, the International Organization for Standardization, the International Electrotechnical Commission, and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). All information security standards have one thing in common: they aim to preserve confidentiality (information should be accessible only to authorized persons), integrity (information should be accurate and not subject to unauthorized modification), and availability (information should be accessible when needed).

The effectiveness of any economic activity, including information security, depends largely on how actively market participants are engaged in standardization processes and utilize standards in their daily work. Standardization brings significant benefits to businesses, helping to reduce costs, save resources, improve a company's reputation, maintain customer trust, facilitate planning and management processes, and enhance competitive advantage. For consumers, standards are important because they help satisfy their demands for the required level of information security [2]. For society as a whole, standardization contributes to increased economic competitiveness, the development of international technological cooperation, and the stimulation of innovation and investment.

Standardization is a key element of the economics of information security. It ensures not only the possibility of obtaining economic benefits but also their preservation and reuse. The economic efficiency of standardization is the ratio of the economic benefit achieved from applying standards to the costs of their development and implementation; this is manifested in reduced costs and increased productivity across the organization and the national economy as a whole. The economic impact of standardization is expressed in reduced costs for software product/system design, development, testing, implementation, and operation.

The following groups of indicators are useful as economic indicators [3]. First, indicators of economic efficiency per unit of output (in monetary or physical units); second, economic efficiency itself, as the ratio of benefits to costs.

The next element of the economics of information security is information security management.

Information security management includes a set of methods and actions applied in practice to meet information security requirements. These measures are aimed at both monitoring the process itself and eliminating the causes of problems at all stages to improve economic efficiency. The philosophy of information security management emphasizes a long-term strategy

focused on customer satisfaction, employee motivation and satisfaction, high-quality operations, and improving the overall performance of companies striving for excellence. In contrast, technical aspects such as information security assurance and compliance are considered only as a part of the overall approach.

Information security management helps ensure profitability, reduce costs, maintain customer loyalty, enhance the organization's reputation and image, and meet production and delivery deadlines for products and services. It promotes business stability and reliability and improves overall efficiency. The economic efficiency of implementing management practices is defined as the ratio of the achieved result (resource savings or profit increase) to the costs of developing and implementing these measures. The primary goal is to optimize business processes, reduce costs, and improve the overall productivity of the organization.

The effectiveness of management efforts and decisions is reflected in specific quantitative indicators reflecting the organization's performance:

- cost reduction: reduction in production costs through savings in semi-variable expenses and resource optimization, primarily through achieving the stability of information systems;
- productivity increase: reduction in the labor intensity of management processes and loss of working time, which occurs as a result of, firstly, the alignment of business processes and, secondly, maintaining the operability of the organization's information systems;
- financial results: increase in the overall value of the business.

The aforementioned fundamental principles of information security economics (standardization and information security management) shape the core activities that comprise the basic tools and methodological framework economics of information security: education and training, forecasting, and evaluation.

Education and training. Addressing the challenges of information security economics requires widespread education and professional training for all segments of society – from the average consumer to professionals at any level. Information security training is not an isolated discipline intended solely for information security specialists. This problem is interdisciplinary in nature and affects everyone, from pupils in schools to retirees. Information security is perhaps one of the few fields today where knowledge is not limited to specialists. On the contrary, there is a pressing need for this knowledge to be disseminated throughout society. An important aspect of information security training is the rapid obsolescence of knowledge. Of course, this isn't just about fundamental, theoretical knowledge. It's about the constant emergence of new threats, new fraudulent schemes, and new technologies that require constant detection and widespread public awareness.

Much attention is being paid to training specialists in information security in many countries. The demand for information security specialists has increased dramatically worldwide. In the Republic of Belarus training specialists in this field is also organized. The author of this article is a lecturer at the Belarusian State University of Informatics and Radioelectronics (BSUIR). BSUIR is particularly proud of its Faculty of Information Security, which dates back to 1980 [4]. The faculty trains specialists capable of ensuring not only the confidentiality, integrity, accessibility, security, and authenticity of information – that is, information protection – but also possesses the relevant knowledge and skills to counter new information security threats emerging in modern society.

Today, the faculty is a leading scientific and educational center in the Republic of Belarus, conducting research and training highly qualified specialists with a thorough knowledge

of information protection and information security methods for the field of information and communications technology. Scientific schools exist and successfully operate within the faculty. In addition to BSUIR, other universities in the Republic of Belarus also train specialists in information security. For example, at the Belarusian State University in the Faculty of Applied Mathematics and Informatics and the Faculty of Radiophysics and Computer Technology; and at the Faculty of Computer Science and Electronics at Euphrosyne Polotskaya Polotsk State University.

Forecasting. In this case, forecasting means developing forecasts focusing on the prospects for information security development. This activity involves taking into account the multifaceted determination of the development of the object under study, as well as the availability of a number of possible options. Forecasting is associated with goal setting, planning, design, and management.

This utilizes three main, complementary sources of information about the future: an assessment of the prospects for the development of information security risks based on experience; the conditional continuation of trends into the future whose development patterns are fairly well known in the past and present (extrapolation); and the creation of a model of the future state of the object or process under study in accordance with the expected or desired change in a number of conditions whose development prospects are fairly well known.

An assessment is a systematic verification of an entity's ability to meet established information security requirements (an information security system audit).

An information security system assessment can be conducted to determine whether a counterparty provides the required level of information security. In this case, depending on specific conditions, the results of the information security assessment can be used for qualification, approval, registration, or accreditation.

Additional qualifiers may be used with the information security assessment, depending on the area of activity (e.g., process, personnel, or the entire system) and timeframe (e.g., until contract expiration). Generally speaking, an information security assessment may also include an assessment of financial and technical resources.

Assessment also includes activities such as assessment and confirmation of compliance (including certification) – proof that specified requirements for a product, process, system or a person have been met.

Thus, the study of economics of information security clearly demonstrates the interplay of disciplines. The phenomenon of economics of information security lies in the complexity of its impact. For example, improving information security reduces costs associated with the loss or theft of data and damage to partner reputation. The economics of information security provides an opportunity to take a fresh look at many phenomena and patterns of social and industrial relations from the perspective of the role of information security and its influence on the course of socio-economic development.

References

1. Князькова, В.С. Направления интеграции системы управления информационной безопасностью в общую стратегию организации / В.С. Князькова // Управление информационными ресурсами: материалы XXI Междунар. науч.-практич. конф. (Республика Беларусь, Минск, 28 марта 2025 года) / редкол.: В.Г. Швайко [и др.]. – Минск : Академия управления при Президенте Республики Беларусь, 2025. – 508 с. – С. 295–296.

2. Бемяцкая, Т. Н. Страхование рисков информационной безопасности / Т. Н. Бемяцкая, В. С. Князькова // Технические средства защиты информации : тез. докл. XVIII Белорус.-рос. науч.-техн. конф., Минск, 9 июня 2020 г. / Белорус. гос. ун-т информатики и радиоэлектроники [и др.] ; редкол.: Т. В. Борботько [и др.]. – Минск, 2020. – С. 15–16.
2. Kennerley, M. Measuring performance in a changing business environment / M. Kennerley, A. Neely // International Journal of Operation & Production Management. – 2003. – Vol. 23, № 2, 2003. – P. 213 – 229.
4. Факультет информационной безопасности. URL: <https://www.bsuir.by/ru/fik>.